

De-carbonization of Market Clusters in Sub Sahara Region: Nkwo Market Nnewi as a Case Study

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Abstract

Emission of carbons in the atmosphere is generated as products of the combustion of fossil fuels from automobiles or the burning of solid fossil fuels. Carbon emission is majorly produced as a product of combustion in the transport cycle and stationary combustion of fossil fuels from automobiles like the Generator sets. Inadequate power supply and epileptic power supply from the public electric power supply, gen-sets become the main source of power supply in Nkwo international market in Nnewi, Anambra State. The international market has motor cycle spare parts market, the motor spare parts market, building material market, the general market which comprises pharmaceuticals, clothes, food items etc. population samples of stores were done, number of the store with Gen set were noted, then using 'bottom up' method the quantity of carbon released and attributed to fuel combustion by the two stroke engine 'I pass my neighbor' using gasoline was calculated, the total estimate of the carbon release in the atmosphere is estimated base on eight working hours. The power estimation is also done to ascertain to suggest the amount of solar energy required to power the market for carbon zero emission free atmosphere.

Key Words: De-carbonization, market clusters, solar energy, zero emission, and Sub-Sahara Africa.

Introduction

The poor narrative of Nigerian electric power supply had forced an average business man and woman, every store or shop owner to own a two stroke engine fondly called, 'I Pass My Neighbour', to run the business. These two stroke engines greatly constitute a public nuisance as they are an agent of pollution –gas CO₂ and noise. Many cases of death have been reported as a result of pollution in private homes. Anthropogenic emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) contribute greatly to global warming potentials, and there are many aspects of the use of gas. The CO₂ reactions produced by the heating oil are high in humans and the catalyst is evaluated directly and indirectly. In addition to the need for adequate CO₂ emissions from fuel efficiency for the collection and monitoring of energy consumption data, emissions are considered important for preparing and monitoring the emissions policy. Simple methods of estimating CO₂ from fuel use assume that the carbon in the fuel used for all activities will enter the environment in the short or long term. The brief examples are described in the IPCC Tentative List as in the two decades since fuel use and in almost all fire-fighting reports. Long-term CO₂ emissions come from the latest long-lived living coal products and are commonly used for waste disposal. A comparative approach to carbon use, which includes the benchmark (RA) and the monitoring method (US), measures and interprets the amount of carbon consumed in space as CO₂. Most products are CO₂, some of which are fertilizers of carbon monoxide (CO), methane (CH₄) and non-methanol (NMVOC). The United Kingdom and the United States are defined as a "crop" in the sense that they determine any electricity from the economy's oil supply or key sectors of the economy rather than being available with oil or internal facts. This work consists of comparing the production of materials for electric motors installed in the Nkwo market in the state of Anambra, Nigeria. By default, mobile content is not included. The increased use of crude oil in all human activities means affecting all sectors of the economy and employment. The number of each store prevents the direct evaluation of the content of each source. However, a large number of generator sets greatly influence the distribution of the sources and the size of the product. CO₂ estimates are obtained by

measuring the number of factories or stores in the market, the number of stores that use generator sets. CO2 emissions estimated by the 10-hour generator and estimated CO2 based on the current market.

Methods Available In Carbon Emission Determination

The division of methods is divided into two, "top-down" and "Bottom up" and methods of measuring electricity, including methodology (United Kingdom) and regional methods (United States) oil heating or actual data in combustion centers. "Below", if there is detailed national information on petroleum production in key industries or food sectors, "weak" detailed information can be provided. When there is detailed information on the fuel consumed in the main food type (s), the "net result" can be calculated as follows:

$$C_r = Q \times NCV \times EF \times (1 - S_f) \times f \quad [i]$$

Where:

Cr: the amount of carbon released for fuel (increase to 44/12 for CO2) \ t

Q: How much fuel is delivered to the vehicle or treated with the activity (component) shown in the ordinary components?

NCV: fuel efficiency (TJ / business unit) \ t

EF: sales information (in particular carbon content, t C / TJ) \ t

Sf indicates a carbon storage material, the supplied carbon content that is not recycled after the use of the oil, regardless of the product produced or not, does not include the carbon dioxide oxidation certificate.

F: the oxidation rate, the carbon content of the oxidation during combustion. Structural methods can be used using the protection information expressed in the C / natural unit and avoid the need for many factors.

The reference approach (AR)

The reference method provides simpler models for CO2 emissions from petroleum fuels that do not provide enough industry or specific data based on detailed petroleum consumption data. AR can be used as a study of all sales results obtained by collecting estimates for a series of activities. The AR estimates the CO2 emissions from combustion engines and certain bulk emissions. It also provides a breakdown of electricity based on the size of the fuel, but the mechanisms by which fuel is used are less clear than the level of fire, in particular, from the main sources of fuel cannot be measured individually. The fuel cell statistics used to determine the oil flow include emissions and thefts from the transportation and consumption of these flows. Oil production in a country is carried out according to the following formula:

$$(production) + imports - export = stock change \quad (ii)$$

Production is included only for primary fuels (see the IPCC Guidelines Vol. 3).

The sectoral approach

The AR Plan does not provide estimates for the main fuel-based element, and as this information is important for disease monitoring and reduction, the same principle was applied "from above" "Supply of oils to the main supply chain as described in IPCC Assistance Program Volume 1. The method was introduced in the IPCC Guide List as a regional level 1. (US) method. CO2 emissions from non-transport products can compare in Part 1 and compare to domestic manufacturers worldwide is only part of the portable distributor series, this feature is not quite accurate as a result of CO2. The sources used are the most important sources and documents of the IPCC guidelines:

- Energy production;
- Production and construction;
- Transportation;
- Registration;
- Agriculture, forestry and fishing e

• Others

“Bottom-up Approach”

“Bottom-up” methods can be very effective when obtaining reliable data from companies that buy or use oil. In general, manufacturing companies with large plants make the flow larger and more satisfying than energy production. The sample results are determined or calculated based on the oil supply data for the department or group of areas where the welfare works are located.

Calorific values and emission factors

The main ingredients are caloric fats and vegetable ingredients (or more precisely, electrolytes). The following table reproduces the values of the different parameters and parameters used in the IPCC Guidelines. If there is significant variation, most of the identified values include the quantity, but not the values. It is clear from the IPCC rule that tariffs are used in many countries for crude oil and natural gas (LNG). Items were generated when EMI changed a site specific site using site specific estimates / percentages. They are 0.95 for coal and oil and 0.9 for gas.

TABLE 1

Net Calorific Values and Emission Factors for Oils as Found in the 1996 IPCC Guidelines

Oil based Fuels	Net Calorific Value (GJ/t	Emission Factor (tC/TJ)
Crude oil	From 41 to 43 GJ / h. Depending on gross margin. 42.6 GJ / h standard. That's not part of it very important to the market The recipe is unusual..	20.0 - 21.0 tC/TJ.
Natural Gas Liquids (ethane, propane, butane and condensate	42 - 45 GJ/t. Composition varies considerably. Typical value 43.5 GJ/t. Local advice needed on NCV.	17.2 tC/TJ. Dependent on composition ranging from about 17.2 for light mixtures to 19.0 for condensate rich mixtures.
Oil Shale	Usually 8.6 – 11.5 GJ/t but larger ranges are quoted.	29.1 tC/TJ (calculated using an NCV of 8.6 GJ/t)
Gasoline	44.8 GJ/t	18.9 tC/TJ
Jet Kerosene	44.59 GJ/t	19.5 tC/TJ
Other Kerosene	44.75 GJ/t	19.6 tC/TJ
Gas/Diesel oil	43.33 GJ/t	20.2 tC/TJ
Residual fuel oil	40.19 GJ/t	21.1 tC/TJ
Shale Oil	40.0 GJ/t	20.5 tC/TJ
LPG	47.31 GJ/t	17.2 tC/TJ
Ethane	47.49 GJ/t	16.8 tC/TJ
Naphtha	N45.01 GJ/t	20.0 (default value)
Lubricants	40.19 GJ/t	20.0 (default value)
Petroleum Coke 31.00 GJ/t 27.5 tC/TJ	31.00 GJ/t	27.5 tC/TJ
Refinery Gas	48.15 GJ/t Composition of gas varies with Refinery and with operations. Local advice needed.	18.2 tC/TJ (see comment on calorific value)

Source : Tim Simmons (Avonlog Limited, UK),

Carbon Storage Factors

The carbon storage unit, a fraction, is used to reduce some of the fuel consumption. The area is considered equivalent to the carbon stored by long-term oil recovery. The material is exposed to oil and its specific use and is used in quantity supplied as raw materials in the chemical industry and in the methods available in this regard. The IPCC guidelines contain information on ethane, LPG, trees, gas / diesel and natural gas, although the figures provided are very close (Table 2).

TABLE 2

Carbon Storage Factors As Given In the 1996 IPCC Guidelines

Fuel types	Storage factor
Ethane	0.8
LPG	0.8
Naphtha	0.8
Gas/Diesel oil	0.5
Natural gas	0.33
Lubricants	0.5

Source: Tim Simmons (Avonlog Limited, UK),

Oxidation factors

Not all carbon is oxidized during combustion. Some can be stored in compost and transported or transported in gas or stored in residue and dust after completion. The oxides are administered at the oxidation stage. The whole oxidation process depends on fuel and waste. It is much higher for natural gas heating and lowers fuel oil consumption. This method is suitable for the production of large compressors depending on the type of heating and cooling equipment.

TABLE 3

Oxidation Factors As Given In the 1996 IPCC Guidelines

Fuel	The fraction of carbon oxidized
Coal	0.98
Oil products	0.99
Gas	0.995
Peat for electricity generation	0.99

Source: Tim Simmons (Avonlog Limited, UK),

The table above shows the values given in the IPCC Guidelines (Table 5). It has a limited scope and there are no burns to homes that can burn crude oil (especially fire and petroleum) under conditions that prevent the burning of carbon and petroleum. The IPCC Guidelines Manual (Vol.3) contains additional information on the combustion of coal in different types of coal. Without the correct numbers for detection, it would set 0.99.

Design Methodology Analysis

The design approach proposed for the determination of carbon emission in the nkwo market is the “Bottom-up Approach”. The assumptions made are based on ideal situation and the data collected are categorized base on a section of the market differentiating those with small gen sets and those without gen set

Assumptions

The following assumptions were made in the population study of nkwo market

- i. That all business men and women come to market every day except Sundays.

- ii. That those with gen sets use their set every day between 8.00a.m to 6,00 pm
- iii. All gen set is the two stroke engines –I pass my neighbor type

Market Description

Nkwo market is situated between umudim ,otolo and uragu nnewi with major access roads ,Onitsha oba old road,Onitsha oba new road, Awka unobi road , ozubulu road where goods and customers flow into the market.

Data Collection

The data collection is done by counting and questioning about if the store has a gen set or attached to a gen set because an individual may have up to 2 to 5 stores. The international market comprises

- a. motor cycle spare parts market,
- b. the motor spare parts market,
- c. building material market,
- d. the general market which comprises pharmaceuticals, clothes, food items et

Table 4. Data collection from nkwo market

S/N	DESCRIPTION	TOTAL NUMBER OF STORES(SHOP)	TOTAL NUMBER OF STORES WITH GEN SET	TOTAL NUMBER OF STOR WITHOUT GEN SET
1	motor cycle spare parts market	6500	5794	706
2	the motor spare parts market,	4860	3980	880
3	building material market,	3268	3198	70
4	the general market	7065	5487	1578
5	Total	21693	18459	3234

Determination of CO2 emission per Generator set

Using the bottom –up approach

$$C_r = Q \times NCV \times EF \times (1 - S_f) \times f$$

Where:

Cr: the amount of carbon released for fuel (increase to 44/12 for CO₂) \ t

Q: How much fuel is delivered to the vehicle or treated with the activity (component) shown in the ordinary components?

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DATA

Q = quantity of fuel in the gen set = 5liters

F=0.99 for oil product

Sf=0.8

EF=18.9 tC/TJ

NCV=44.8 GJ/t

Every day it is assumed the every generator user spend 10hrs, a full tank of the type of small gen set takes 8hrs

Determining the volume of fuel to be spent in 10hrs

$$\frac{4}{8} = \frac{x}{10}$$

$$x = 5liters$$

From the equation

$$C_r = Q \times NCV \times EF \times (1 - S_f) \times f$$

		Multiplying factors		quantity of carbon released Cr
quantity of fuel delivered to generator Q	5000			
: the net calorific value of fuel NCV	44.8			
emission factor EF	18.9			
: carbon storage factor(1-0.8)	0.2			
the oxidation factor	0.99			
TOTAL GASEOUS EMISSION	838252.8	44	12	3073593.6

Hence, the total number quantity of carbon emitted per day

$$C_r \text{ carbon} = C_r \times 10hrs = 30735936cm^3$$

This implies an approximate amount of CO₂ release daily into the atmosphere at nkwo international market is 30735936cm³

De-carbonization

To start decarbonizing the market there must be a sensitization campaign where the inherent dangers of carbon dioxide, carbon mono oxide and other constituent gases emitted are addressed to the nkwo marketers. An alternative source of clean energy that has zero emission and noise free is introduced. Solar energy consumption is the sure alternative to be introduced; the power consumption of the market can be estimated from the numbers of stores with gen sets in the market. This will however give an estimated value of the energy but we should not forget the safety value. Therefore, making the market a green community is developing a solar farm for each interested group until it is embraced because the long run cost effect is zero. Solar electricity systems are costly, hence acquiring them is always discouraged by cost but if ventured the long run is always zero cost. Maintenance is easy and you can grow the system to the capacity desired. Health benefit is not doubted since respiratory diseases related problems that might have resulted from the inhalation of the emissions have been eliminated through zero emission of the solar energy system.

Conclusion

Nkwo international market is large and businesses thrive when there is equitable power supply. Many markets in Nigeria and the rest of Sub Sahara Africa are suffering from the poor or epileptic power supply. They therefore have no option than to depend on fossil fuel dependent power generation. Hence, Sub Sahara Africa being a growing economy will be in dire need of power, to decarbonize these market clusters, sensitization campaigns on renewable energy, the use of solar energy for power generation, there should be a collaboration between banks on loans for the acquisition of solar energy systems for the business men and women. This will help to de-carbonize these market clusters and based on the amount of carbon release into the atmosphere, it implies these market clusters contribute greatly to the carbonization of the environment.

Reference

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